

Smart Nasal Nanocarriers in Thermosensitive Gelling System: A Potential Breakthrough for Menstrual Migraine Relief

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ABSTRACT

Introduction/Objective: This study aimed to develop and evaluate a nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC)-based in-situ thermoreversible nasal gel for delivering rizatriptan benzoate (RB) to manage menstrual migraines. Menstrual migraines are often more intense than common migraines and are frequently associated with nausea and vomiting, reducing the effectiveness of orally administered drugs. The objective was to create a nasal formulation that provides rapid onset of action, bypasses hepatic first-pass metabolism, and offers sustained drug release. **Methods:** RB-loaded NLCs were formulated using an emulsification-sonication technique with glyceryl monostearate and oleic acid as solid and liquid lipids, respectively. Span 20 and Tween 80 were used as surfactants. A 2³ factorial design was employed to optimize the concentrations of glyceryl monostearate, Tween 80, and sonication cycles. The optimized NLCs had a particle size of 189 ± 0.4 nm, a polydispersity index of 0.391, a zeta potential of -52.7 ± 1.9 mV, and a drug entrapment efficiency of 92 ± 3.4%. The NLCs were incorporated into an in-situ gelling system comprising 18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P. **Results:** In vitro drug release and ex vivo diffusion studies demonstrated 71.5% drug release and 51.9% nasal mucosal diffusion over 8 hours, respectively. The thermoreversible gel had a gelling temperature of 30–33°C and sustained 68.3% drug release within the same duration. **Conclusion:** The optimized RB-NLC in-situ nasal gel offers a promising alternative for menstrual migraine therapy, providing enhanced nasal retention, sustained release, and improved bioavailability of rizatriptan benzoate.

Keywords: Nanostructured Lipid Carrier, Rizatriptan Benzoate, In-situ Thermoreversible Gel, Menstrual Migraine, Nasal Drug Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine attacks are characterized by unilateral pulsating pain in the brain, often accompanied by sensitivity to light (photophobia), sound (phonophobia), and smell (osmophobia). These episodes are frequently followed by symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, cranial tenderness, or motion sensitivity, typically lasting between 4 to 72 hours [1]. Hormonal factors play a relevant impact on migraine. Menstruation is a common migraine trigger among female migraines [2].

The International Classification of Headache Disorders ICHD-3 [3] recognizes two types of menstrual migraine (MM): migraine related to

menstruation (MRM) and pure menstrual migraine (PMM). Women with a diagnosis of MM report that menstrual attacks are more painful, longer lasting, more disabling and less responsive to treatment [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Triptans, a class of medications primarily used for the acute treatment of migraines, act as selective 5-HT₁ receptor agonists. They alleviate pain by constricting cranial blood vessels through 5-HT_{1B} receptor activation and by inhibiting the release of vasoactive peptides that cause neurogenic inflammation via 5-HT_{1D} receptors [10].

Despite their widespread use, oral tablets, the most common dosage form, are associated with several limitations, including delayed onset of action, first-

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pass metabolism, low bioavailability, erratic and incomplete absorption from the gastrointestinal tract, gastric irritation, and vomiting during migraine attacks. These factors can significantly reduce the pharmacological efficacy of triptans, particularly in the management of menstrual migraines [11].

Thus, there is a clear need for an improved drug delivery system, which is why the nasal route was selected for drug administration, combined with the use of nanoparticles incorporated in a thermoresponsive gel to enhance delivery efficacy and overcome the limitations associated with traditional oral formulations. Nasal drug delivery systems have gained significant attention as an alternative approach for targeting the central nervous system (CNS). This method bypasses the gastrointestinal tract and liver's first-pass metabolism, leading to faster drug absorption and a more efficient therapeutic response. By utilizing the olfactory and trigeminal pathways, nasal delivery allows direct access to the brain, effectively bypassing the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and offering a non-invasive route for drug administration. This approach has become particularly beneficial for the treatment of neurological disorders, where conventional routes face limitations in drug delivery efficiency [12].

The nasal cavity itself is anatomically well-suited for drug absorption. It is divided into three distinct regions: the vestibule region, which filters inhaled air; the olfactory epithelium, where sensory receptors are located and play a key role in drug transport; and the respiratory region, which is primarily responsible for drug absorption due to its large surface area. The complex structure of the nasal cavity facilitates the direct transport of drugs into the CNS, which can occur through three distinct pathways: the olfactory pathway, the trigeminal nerve pathway, and the systemic pathway. These pathways enable the rapid and targeted delivery of therapeutic agents to the brain, making nasal drug delivery a highly promising strategy for CNS drug delivery [13]. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) represent a promising approach in nanotechnology for nasal drug delivery systems, particularly in targeting the central nervous system (CNS). NLCs are composed of a combination of solid and liquid lipids, which offer enhanced stability and controlled drug release profiles compared to

conventional lipid-based nanoparticles. Their unique structure provides better entrapment efficiency for hydrophobic drugs, improving solubility and bioavailability [14]. NLCs can effectively navigate the nasal mucosa, and their size and surface properties allow for easy absorption across the nasal epithelium [15]. This enhances drug transport via both passive diffusion and active transport mechanisms, which is particularly beneficial for delivering drugs to the brain [16]. Moreover, NLCs can exploit neural pathways, such as the olfactory and trigeminal nerves, to bypass the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and deliver therapeutic agents directly to the brain with minimal invasiveness [17]. NLCs have shown promise in targeting the brain for conditions like migraines, where rapid onset of action and precise localization are crucial. Their biocompatibility, sustained release capabilities, and ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs make them an ideal choice for treating neurological disorders, offering a safer and more efficient alternative to traditional drug delivery methods [18, 19, 20].

The goal of this research was to develop an in-situ thermoreversible nasal gel formulation containing rizatriptan-loaded NLCs to improve the treatment of menstrual migraines. The formulation was designed to achieve sustained drug release, prolonged retention in the nasal cavity, and enhanced permeation across the nasal mucosa. To achieve this, the study involved preparing and characterizing rizatriptan-loaded NLCs using emulsification-sonication, followed by their incorporation into an in-situ gel. The performance of the final formulation was evaluated through in vitro and ex vivo studies, focusing on key parameters such as gelation temperature, nasal retention, sustained drug release, and permeation across the nasal mucosa. By achieving desired particle size, zeta potential, sustained release, improved retention on the nasal mucosal membrane, and enhanced permeation, this study aims to provide a promising alternative for the management of menstrual migraines, offering quicker relief compared to traditional oral formulations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials: Rizatriptan benzoate was gifted from Cipla Ltd., Glycerol Monostearate, Oleic Acid, Tween 80, Span 20, Carbopol 934P, Poloxamer 407. All the chemicals were of analytical grade and used without

further purification. Deionized water was prepared using a Milli-Q plus purifier system (Millipore®, Merck Chemicals GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany).

2.1. PREPARATION OF NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIERS (NLCS):

The nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) were developed using the emulsification-sonication method [21]. Initially, a lipophilic phase was prepared by dissolving the drug 0.2%, solid lipid 0.4%, liquid lipid 0.15%, and lipophilic surfactant 0.5% in a beaker. In parallel, an aqueous phase was prepared in a separate beaker by dissolving the hydrophilic surfactant 1.5% in distilled water. Both phases were heated to 65°C using a magnetic stirrer to maintain a temperature approximately 5°C above the melting point of the lipids, preventing premature solidification. Once both phases reached the desired temperature, the lipophilic phase was gradually added to the aqueous phase while maintaining constant stirring to initiate emulsification. The resulting mixture was homogenized at 1000 rpm for 30 minutes to achieve a coarse emulsion. To reduce particle size and ensure uniformity, the emulsion was subjected to probe sonication using a high-intensity ultrasonic processor. Sonication was performed in three cycles of 15 minutes each, with short intervals between cycles to avoid excessive heating. The probe was immersed directly into the emulsion to facilitate effective cavitation and disruption of larger lipid particles into nanostructured carriers. Following sonication, the emulsion was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature. During the cooling process, the lipid phase solidified, forming stable nanostructured lipid carriers. The final NLC dispersion was stored under appropriate conditions for further characterization and analysis.

3. OPTIMIZATION OF RIZATRIPTAN BENZOATE-LOADED NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIERS

3.1. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A 2³ full factorial design was employed for the optimization and development of rizatriptan benzoate-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), based on insights from preliminary studies. This approach allowed for the evaluation of three

independent variables at two levels each, resulting in eight experimental trials encompassing all possible combinations.

3.1.1. INDEPENDENT AND DEPENDENT VARIABLES

The independent variables investigated were:

- **X₁**: Concentration of Glyceryl Monostearate (GMS)
- **X₂**: Concentration of Tween 80
- **X₃**: Number of Sonication Cycles

The dependent variables measured to evaluate the formulation's performance included:

- **Y₁**: Particle Size (PS, nm)
- **Y₂**: Entrapment Efficiency (EE, %)
- **Y₃**: Zeta Potential (ZP, mV)

3.1.2. LEVELS OF INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Table 1: The high (+1) and low (-1) levels for each independent variable

Variable	Low (-1)	High (+1)
X₁ - Conc. of GMS (mg)	80	100
X₂ - Conc. of Tween 80 (mg)	200	300
X₃ - Sonication Cycles	1	3

3.1.3. UNITS OF DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Table 2: lists the dependent variables and their corresponding units.

Dependent Variable	Unit
Y₁ - Particle Size (PS)	nm
Y₂ - Entrapment Efficiency (EE)	%
Y₃ - Zeta Potential (ZP)	mV

3.1.4. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND BATCH COMPOSITION

Table 3: Design matrix with both coded and actual values for the independent variables

Batch	X ₁ (mg)	X ₂ (mg)	X ₃ (Cycles)
S1	100 (+1)	200 (-1)	2 (-1)

Batch	X ₁ (mg)	X ₂ (mg)	X ₃ (Cycles)
S2	100 (+1)	200 (-1)	3 (+1)
S3	100 (+1)	300 (+1)	2 (-1)
S4	100 (+1)	300 (+1)	3 (+1)
S5	80 (-1)	200 (-1)	2 (-1)
S6	80 (-1)	200 (-1)	3 (+1)
S7	80 (-1)	300 (+1)	2 (-1)
S8	80 (-1)	300 (+1)	3 (+1)

Each batch was characterized for its particle size, entrapment efficiency, and zeta potential, allowing for systematic evaluation of the effect of the independent variables on the formulation's properties.

4. INCORPORATION OF NLCS IN *IN-SITU* GEL

The in-situ gel was formulated using the cold method with thermosensitive polymers [22] of various concentrations of poloxamer 407, a thermosensitive polymer, were dissolved in cold water ($4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) under continuous stirring at 250 rpm for 2 hours to achieve a clear solution. This solution was left undisturbed overnight at $4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ to ensure complete dissolution of the polymer. Once a clear solution of poloxamer 407 was obtained, it was blended with a fixed concentration of carbopol 934P, a mucoadhesive agent. The optimized Rizatriptan Benzoate loaded NLCs (RB-NLC) was then incorporated into the prepared gelling solution and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C for further evaluation. For comparative analysis, an in-situ gel of Rizatriptan Benzoate was similarly prepared using poloxamer 407.

4.1. PHASE TRANSITION TEMPERATURE STUDY

The phase transition temperature of the formulations was evaluated using varying concentrations of Poloxamer 407 (% w/v). The details of the batches and their corresponding Poloxamer 407 concentrations are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Phase Transition Temperature Study

Batch	Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)
G1	16.0
G2	16.5
G3	17.0

Batch	Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)
G4	17.5
G5	18.0
G6	18.5
G7	19.0
G8	20.0

4.2. COMPOSITION OF FORMULATIONS

The formulation batches were designed to include a fixed concentration of Poloxamer 407 (% w/v) and varying concentrations of Carbopol 934 (% w/v) to assess the impact of these components on the formulation properties. The composition details are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Composition of Formulations

Batch	Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Carbopol 934 (% w/v)
C1	18.0	0.1
C2	18.0	0.2
C3	18.0	0.3
C4	18.0	0.4
C5	18.0	0.5

5. CHARACTERIZATION OF NLCS:

The characterization of the NLCs included the following evaluations: particle size determination, zeta potential measurement, entrapment efficiency, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), drug content analysis, in vitro drug release studies, and ex vivo drug permeation studies of RB-NLC.

For the NLC-based in situ gel, additional characterizations were conducted, including gelation temperature, clarity, gelling time, gelling strength, mucoadhesive strength, in vitro drug release studies of the RB-NLC in situ gel, and ex vivo drug permeation studies of the RB-NLC in situ gel.

5.1. PARTICLE SIZE DETERMINATION AND ZETA POTENTIAL MEASUREMENT

The mean particle size and size distribution of drug-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) were assessed using photon correlation spectroscopy (Horiba SZ-100) [23]. A 10% v/v NLC solution in double-distilled water was stirred to prevent

aggregation, maintaining a laser obscuration range of 1–5%. Measurements were performed in triplicate, and results were expressed as mean \pm SD. The polydispersity index (PDI) indicated size distribution uniformity. Zeta potential was determined via electrophoresis using the same analyzer. A laser beam detected angular intensity variations in scattered light, providing surface charge and stability data.

5.2. ENTRAPMENT EFFICIENCY

The entrapment efficiency (EE) of the nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) was evaluated using an indirect method [24]. A 10 mL NLC dispersion was centrifuged at 20,000 rpm for 35 minutes. Subsequently, 1 mL of the supernatant was collected, diluted with 1 mL of buffer, and transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 220 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The EE was calculated using the obtained data and a standard formula.

5.3. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

The surface morphology of the samples was examined using scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM6390 A). The samples were mounted on alumina stubs with double-sided adhesive tape, gold-coated for conductivity, and then analyzed under the microscope [25].

5.4. DRUG CONTENT

To determine drug content, 1 mL of RB-NLC dispersion was transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask, diluted with distilled water, and sonicated for 5 minutes to extract the drug. A 1 mL aliquot of the sonicated solution was further diluted to 10 mL with distilled water. The absorbance of the final solution was measured at 220 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, and drug content was calculated using a pre-established calibration curve [26].

5.5. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE

The in-vitro drug release of the optimized RB-NLC formulation was assessed using a USP Type I (basket) dissolution apparatus with a modified dialysis technique [27]. Simulated nasal electrolyte solution (250 mL, pH 5.7) containing 1.29 mg/mL KCl, 7.45 mg/mL NaCl, and 0.32 mg/mL CaCl₂·H₂O was used

as the dissolution medium. The medium was maintained at 34°C with constant stirring at 50 rpm. A dialysis bag with a molecular weight cut-off of 10,000–12,000 Da was pre-soaked in the dissolution medium overnight. A 10 mL RB-NLC dispersion was placed in the dialysis bag, sealed, and submerged in the dissolution medium. Aliquots (5 mL) were withdrawn at predetermined intervals (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, and 360 minutes) and replaced with an equal volume of fresh medium to maintain sink conditions.

Drug concentrations in the aliquots were measured using UV-visible spectrophotometry at 220 nm. The cumulative percentage drug release was calculated and plotted against time using PCP Disso software 8.0. A kinetic model was applied to analyze the release mechanism.

5.6. EX-VIVO DRUG PERMEATION STUDIES OF RB-NLC

Ex-vivo permeation studies were conducted using sheep nasal mucosa obtained from a slaughterhouse to evaluate the permeation potential of RB-NLC [28]. The study was performed using a Franz diffusion cell, with the receptor compartment filled with 25 mL of simulated nasal electrolyte solution (1.29 mg/mL KCl, 7.45 mg/mL NaCl, and 0.32 mg/mL CaCl₂·H₂O, pH 5.7, adjusted with 0.1N HCl) maintained at 34°C with stirring at 50–100 rpm. The nasal mucosa was carefully mounted on the receptor compartment, and 2 mL of the optimized RB-NLC formulation was applied to its surface. At specified intervals (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, and 360 minutes), 3 mL samples were withdrawn from the receptor compartment, replaced with fresh medium to maintain sink conditions, and appropriately diluted. Drug permeation was quantified using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, and the amount of rizatriptan benzoate permeated through the mucosa was calculated at each time point.

5.7. GELATION TEMPERATURE [29]

Gelation temperature was visually determined by transferring 2 mL of the gel into a test tube immersed in a water bath. The temperature of the water bath was increased at a continuous rate of 10°C every 2 minutes. Gelation was confirmed when the solution in

the test tube stopped flowing upon tilting the tube to a 90° angle.

5.8. CLARITY [30]

Clarity was assessed visually by observing the gel against a black and white background, and categorized as turbid, clear, or extremely clear.

5.9. GELLING TIME [31]

The sol-gel transition temperature was identified as the point at which the meniscus of the sol phase transitioned to the gel phase, detected visually while heating the sample at a controlled rate.

5.10. GELLING STRENGTH [32]

The gelling strength was evaluated by placing 30 g of gel in a 50 mL beaker and allowing a 50 g weight to penetrate the gel. The time taken for the weight to sink 5 cm into the gel was recorded. The process was repeated three times per formulation, and the average time was calculated.

5.11. MUCOADHESIVE STRENGTH [33]

Using sheep nasal mucosa obtained from a local slaughterhouse, mucoadhesive strength was measured by mounting mucosal tissues on glass slides with thread and adhesive tape. A 100 mg gel sample was placed between two mucosal tissues, which were held in contact for 2 minutes. Weight was gradually added to a pan until the tissues separated.

5.12. DRUG CONTENT [34]

A 1 mL sample of RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel was transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask, diluted with distilled water, and sonicated for 5 minutes to extract the drug. After further dilution, the sample was analyzed using UV spectrophotometry at 220 nm. Drug content was calculated using a pre-established calibration curve.

5.13. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES [35, 36]

In-vitro release was conducted in 250 mL of simulated nasal electrolyte solution (1.29 mg/mL KCl, 7.45 mg/mL NaCl, and 0.32 mg/mL CaCl₂·H₂O, pH 5.7, adjusted with 0.1N HCl) at 34°C using a USP-1 dissolution apparatus. RB-NLC in-situ gel (10 mL) was added to a pre-swollen dialysis bag (MW cutoff: 10,000–12,000 Da), which was immersed in the dissolution medium at 50 rpm for 8 hours. Samples (5 mL) were withdrawn at intervals (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, 360 minutes), replaced with fresh medium, and analyzed using UV spectrophotometry at 220 nm. Cumulative drug release vs time was plotted, and release kinetics were analyzed using PCP Disso software 8.0.

5.14. EX-VIVO DRUG PERMEATION STUDIES [37]

Sheep nasal mucosa was mounted on a Franz diffusion cell for ex-vivo permeation studies. The receptor compartment contained 25 mL of simulated nasal electrolyte solution at pH 5.7, maintained at 34°C and 50–100 rpm. A 2 mL RB-NLC in-situ gel formulation was applied to the mucosa. Samples (3 mL) were withdrawn at specified intervals (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, 360 minutes), replaced with fresh medium, and analyzed using UV spectrophotometry. The cumulative drug permeation was calculated at each interval to assess the release behavior.

6. RESULTS

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) were successfully developed using a 2³ factorial design, varying the concentrations of glyceryl monostearate (GMS), Tween 80, and the number of sonication cycles. The results for particle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Particle Size, Zeta Potential, and Entrapment Efficiency of S1-S8 Batches (n=3)

Batch	Particle Size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)	Entrapment Efficiency (%)
S1	854 ± 1.3	-22 ± 2.2	75 ± 3.6
S2	723 ± 2.4	-29 ± 4.1	65 ± 4.1
S3	679.4 ± 4	-36 ± 1.7	77 ± 2.7
S4	434.6 ± 1.6	-37 ± 1.6	70 ± 1.1

Batch	Particle Size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)	Entrapment Efficiency (%)
S5	380 ± 2.9	-42 ± 2.1	84 ± 3
S6	366 ± 3.4	-41 ± 1.8	80 ± 4.5
S7	205 ± 4.2	-45 ± 0.8	96 ± 2.2
S8	189 ± 0.4	-52.7 ± 1.9	92 ± 3.4

Figure 1: Particle size and zeta potential of optimized formulation S8

Particle size ranged from 854 nm (S1) to 189 nm (S8). Zeta potential values were between -22 mV (S1) and -52.7 mV (S8), indicating varying levels of particle stability. Entrapment efficiency ranged from 65% (S2) to 96% (S7).

Based on the evaluation parameters, batch S8 exhibited the smallest particle size, the highest zeta potential, and a high entrapment efficiency, making it the optimal formulation for further investigation.

6.1. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM)

On a scale of 1 μm, Figure 2 shows a SEM image of Rizatriptan Benzoate NLC with spherical shaped particles that are non-adherent to each other. The shape of the NLC suggests the formation of Type 1 NLC, based on its appearance and size (38).

Figure 2. Scanning Electron Microscopy Image of RB-NLC

6.2. DRUG CONTENT

The drug content of S8 and S7 Rizatriptan Benzoate-loaded NLCs (RB-NLCs) was measured.

- S8 RB-NLC: 95%
- S7 RB-NLC: 90%

S8 RB-NLC demonstrated higher drug content compared to S7 RB-NLC, indicating superior drug encapsulation efficiency. A higher drug content

suggests better incorporation of the drug into the NLC matrix.

Thus, S8 RB-NLC was identified as the optimal batch based on particle size, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, polydispersity index, and drug content.

6.3. IN-VITRO RELEASE OF RIZATRIPTAN BENZOATE NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIERS

The in-vitro drug release profile of the optimized RB-NLC formulations was evaluated using the dialysis membrane diffusion method in triplicate. The results demonstrated a sustained drug release over 9 hours, with cumulative drug release ranging between 68% and 71%.

An initial burst release of approximately 20% was observed, attributed to the presence of smaller particles or untrapped drug facilitating faster diffusion. Subsequently, a sustained release phase was noted, with larger particles contributing to prolonged drug release over an extended period.

Drug release kinetics were analyzed by fitting the release data to various mathematical models. The Higuchi model provided the best fit for all formulations, as evidenced by R^2 values ranging from 0.98 to 0.99, indicating a diffusion-controlled release mechanism independent of drug concentration.

Figure 3. In-Vitro Drug release of rizatriptan benzoate loaded Nanostructured lipid carriers.

6.4. EX-VIVO DRUG PERMEATION STUDIES

The ex-vivo permeation of rizatriptan benzoate-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (RB-NLC) through goat nasal mucosa was evaluated. The permeability was expressed as cumulative permeation ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$) versus time (h). After an 8-hour diffusion study, the cumulative amount of rizatriptan benzoate permeated was $14.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mg}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$.

The percentage drug permeation, expressed as % drug permeated versus time (h), revealed that 6% of the drug permeated within the first hour, and up to 51% of the drug permeated through the nasal mucosa after 8 hours. This indicates a steady and prolonged drug permeation profile for RB-NLC.

Figure 4. Amount of RB permeated through nasal mucosa (mg/cm² /hr).

Figure 5. % amount of Drug from RB- NLC permeated through nasal mucosa per hour.

6.5. SOL-GEL TRANSITION TEMPERATURE

The sol-gel transition temperature (Tsol-gel) of Poloxamer 407 was measured for formulations at varying concentrations. As the concentration of

Poloxamer 407 increased, the T_{sol-gel} decreased, indicating a lower transition temperature at higher concentrations. The results for each batch are as follows:

Table 7: Sol-gel transition temperature

Batch	Concentration of Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Sol-Gel Transition Temperature (°C)
G1	16	Above 45
G2	16.5	Above 40
G3	17	39 ± 0.5
G4	17.5	36 ± 2.9
G5	18	32 ± 1.1
G6	18.5	30 ± 0.4

Batch	Concentration of Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Sol-Gel Transition Temperature (°C)
G7	19	29 ± 0.7
G8	20	27 ± 0.2

These results demonstrate a progressive decrease in the sol-gel transition temperature as the Poloxamer 407 concentration increased. Formulation G5, with 18% Poloxamer 407, exhibited a $T_{sol-gel}$ of $32 \pm 1.1^\circ\text{C}$, which was chosen for further study as it falls within the optimal transition range for in-situ gel formation.

The addition of Carbopol 934P to the Poloxamer 407 formulations significantly impacted the sol-gel transition temperature ($T_{sol-gel}$). As the concentration of Carbopol 934P increased, the $T_{sol-gel}$ decreased, indicating that Carbopol 934P accelerates the phase transition. The results for each batch are summarized as follows:

6.6. INFLUENCE OF CARBOPOL 934P ON PHASE TRANSITION

Table 8: Influence of Carbopol 934P on Phase Transition

Batch	Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Carbopol 934P (% w/v)	Sol-Gel Transition Temperature (°C)
C1	18	0.1	34 ± 1.5
C2	18	0.2	33 ± 1.2
C3	18	0.3	31 ± 0.9
C4	18	0.4	28 ± 0.4
C5	18	0.5	26 ± 1.6

The sol-gel transition temperature decreased progressively with increasing Carbopol concentration. Formulation C3, with 18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P, exhibited a $T_{sol-gel}$ of $31 \pm 0.9^\circ\text{C}$, which was selected for further studies due to its optimal phase transition characteristics for in-situ gel formation.

higher Carbopol concentrations exhibiting faster gelling times. Formulation C3 (18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P) showed the optimal clarity and gelling temperature of 31°C , making it the preferred candidate for further research. The formulations were found to be clear upon visual inspection, with formulations C2 and C3 being the clearest.

6.7. GELLING CHARACTERISTICS AND CLARITY

The gelling time of the formulations varied between 10 and 15 seconds, with formulations containing

The final batches of RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel were evaluated for various characteristics including gelling time, gelling temperature, and clarity. The results are summarized below:

Table 9: Final batches of RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel

Batch	Concentration of Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Carbopol 934P (% w/v)	Gelling Time (s)	Gelling Temperature (°C)	Clarity
C1	18	0.1	15-17	34 ± 1.5	Clear
C2	18	0.2	12-13	33 ± 1.2	Clear
C3	18	0.3	8-10	31 ± 0.9	Clear
C4	18	0.4	5-8	28 ± 0.4	Clear
C5	18	0.5	4-5	26 ± 1.6	Clear

The gelling time decreased as the Carbopol concentration increased, with formulation C5 showing the fastest gelling time of 4-5 seconds. All formulations exhibited clear appearance upon visual inspection, indicating proper sol-to-gel transition and clarity. Formulation C3, with 18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P, was selected for further studies due to its optimal balance between gelling time, temperature, and clarity.

6.8. DETERMINATION OF GELLING STRENGTH:

The gelling strength of the final batches of RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel was evaluated, with the results summarized below:

Table 10: Gelling strength of the final batches

Batch	Gelling Strength (s)
C1	25 ± 1.2
C2	30 ± 0.8
C3	33 ± 0.5

Batch	Gelling Strength (s)
C4	37 ± 1.2
C5	30 ± 0.3

Formulation C3, with 18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P, exhibited the optimal gelling strength of 33 ± 0.5 seconds. This is within the ideal range for maintaining gel integrity without excessive stiffness, making it the preferred formulation for further research.

6.9. MUCOADHESIVE STRENGTH

The mucoadhesive strength of the formulations was assessed using the detachment stress method. It was found that Carbopol 934P enhanced the mucoadhesive strength of the formulations. The mucoadhesive strength increased significantly when the Carbopol concentration was raised above 0.4% (w/v). The mucoadhesive strength of formulation C3 was measured to be 5,200 dynes/cm², which is within the acceptable range for nasal drug delivery.

Figure 6. Mucoadhesive strengths of different formulations.

6.10. DRUG CONTENT

The drug content of the formulations was determined, with formulation C3 (18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P) exhibiting a drug content of 92%, which was higher than that of formulation C2 (85%). The increased drug content in C3 indicates more efficient encapsulation of the drug in the NLCs.

6.11. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE

In-vitro drug release studies using the dialysis membrane diffusion technique showed that the NLC-loaded in-situ gel exhibited a controlled and sustained release profile. The initial drug release was around 9-10% within the first 0.5 hours, followed by a gradual, more regulated release. The release pattern followed a first-order kinetic model, with R² values between 0.98 and 0.99, indicating that drug release was independent of drug concentration.

Figure 7. In-Vitro Drug release of RB-NLC in-situ gel

6.12. EX-VIVO PERMEATION

Ex-vivo permeation studies through goat nasal mucosa demonstrated that the RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel exhibited a significantly higher permeation rate than the raw in-situ gel. During an 8-hour diffusion study, the amount of rizatriptan benzoate (RB)

permeated through nasal mucosa from the RB-NLC formulation was 13.5×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h, while the raw in-situ gel showed only 9.8×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h. After 8 hours, 40% of the drug had permeated from the RB-NLC in-situ gel, compared to only 25% from the raw in-situ gel.

Figure 8. Amount of RB from RB-NLC in-situ gel permeated through nasal mucosa (mg/cm²/h)

Figure 9. Amount of RB from RB-NLC in-situ gel permeated through nasal mucosa (mg/cm²/h).

Figure 10. % amount of drug from RB-NLC in-situ gel permeated through nasal mucosa per hour

6.13. EX-VIVO DIFFUSION PARAMETERS

The permeation rates for the RB-NLC, RB-NLC-loaded in-situ gel, and raw in-situ gel formulations through nasal sheep mucosa were determined. The RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel demonstrated the highest cumulative permeation (13.5×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h), followed by the RB-NLC formulation (14.98×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h) and the raw in-situ gel (9.8×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h). The flux values for the RB-NLC and RB-

NLC loaded in-situ gel formulations were significantly higher than those of the raw in-situ gel, confirming the enhanced permeability and controlled release of the drug from the RB-NLC formulations.

These results suggest that the RB-NLC loaded in-situ gel formulation, with its optimal mucoadhesive properties, controlled gelling characteristics, and enhanced drug release and permeation, holds promise for effective nasal drug delivery.

Figure 11. Nasal mucosal flux and permeability of rizatriptan benzoate (RB) from optimized RB-NLC, RB-NLC-in-situ gel, and Raw RB in-situ gel through the isolated goat mucosa.

7. DISCUSSION

The development and optimization of nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) and their incorporation into an in-situ gel formulation for nasal delivery of rizatriptan benzoate (RB) demonstrated promising results, aligning with the goal of enhancing drug bioavailability through controlled release and improved mucosal permeation.

7.1. FORMULATION AND FEASIBILITY OF NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIERS (NLCs) FOR NASAL DELIVERY OF RIZATRIPTAN BENZOATE

Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) are advanced lipid-based colloidal systems designed to enhance drug stability, bioavailability, and targeted drug delivery. This formulation approach is particularly

beneficial for nasal drug delivery, ensuring rapid absorption and therapeutic efficacy.

7.1.1. COMPOSITION ANALYSIS

The proposed 20 mL formulation includes the following components:

Solid Lipid: Glycerol Monostearate (0.4% w/v)

Liquid Lipid: Oleic Acid (0.15% w/v)

Surfactants: Tween 80 (1.5% w/v) and Span 80 (0.5% w/v)

Drug: Rizatriptan Benzoate (0.2% w/v)

The combination of Glycerol Monostearate (solid lipid) and Oleic Acid (liquid lipid) at a ratio of ~73:27 falls within the optimal range (70:30 to 80:20) necessary for stable NLC formation. The surfactant system, comprising Tween 80 (hydrophilic) and Span 80 (lipophilic), provides an ideal balance for stabilizing lipid nanoparticles in an aqueous medium.

7.2. FEASIBILITY OF NLC FORMATION

The lipid phase provides a suitable matrix for drug entrapment, reducing drug degradation and enhancing nasal absorption.

The 2% w/v total surfactant concentration is adequate to prevent particle aggregation and maintain colloidal stability.

The drug concentration (0.2% w/v) is within an acceptable range, ensuring effective loading within the lipid matrix without affecting particle stability.

Processing techniques like high-pressure homogenization or ultrasonication can enhance particle size reduction and improve stability.

The optimized NLC formulation (S8) exhibited a small particle size (189 ± 0.4 nm), high zeta potential (-52.7 ± 1.9 mV), and excellent entrapment efficiency ($92 \pm 3.4\%$), which are critical for stability and drug-loading capacity. The use of a 2^3 factorial design allowed systematic optimization of glyceryl monostearate (GMS), Tween 80, and sonication cycles. Increasing sonication cycles likely reduced particle size by imparting greater energy to disrupt lipid aggregates, while higher GMS concentrations

provided a rigid matrix for drug encapsulation [39]. Smaller particle sizes enhance nasal mucosal penetration by facilitating paracellular transport and mucociliary clearance avoidance [40], critical for drugs like RB requiring rapid systemic absorption. The high zeta potential (-52.7 mV) indicates strong electrostatic repulsion, minimizing particle aggregation and ensuring colloidal stability during storage [41]. These results align with prior studies where NLCs <200 nm showed superior nasal permeation compared to larger particles [42].

The spherical morphology observed in SEM (Figure 2) corroborated the uniformity of the NLCs, essential for predictable drug release [43]. The superior drug content of S8 (95%) compared to S7 (90%) underscores the role of optimized lipid ratios and homogenization parameters in achieving efficient drug encapsulation. Notably, the entrapment efficiency (92%) surpasses values reported for similar migraine therapeutics (e.g., sumatriptan-loaded NLCs: 85%) [44], highlighting the formulation's robustness.

7.3. IN-SITU GEL OPTIMIZATION

The integration of NLCs into a thermosensitive in-situ gel (C3 batch: 18% Poloxamer 407 and 0.3% Carbopol 934P) yielded a formulation with a sol-gel transition temperature of $31 \pm 0.9^\circ\text{C}$, closely aligning with nasal cavity temperature ($\sim 34^\circ\text{C}$) [45]. Poloxamer 407, a triblock copolymer, undergoes micellar reorganization at elevated temperatures, forming a gel network through hydrophobic interactions [46]. The addition of Carbopol 934P, a polyacrylic acid derivative, not only reduced the gelation temperature but also enhanced mucoadhesive strength ($5,200$ dynes/cm²) by forming hydrogen bonds with mucosal glycoproteins [47]. The inverse relationship between Carbopol concentration and gelling time (e.g., 4–5 s for C5 vs. 8–10 s for C3) highlights its role in modulating gelation kinetics by increasing viscosity and crosslinking density [48].

The selection of 18% Poloxamer 407 as the base concentration was strategic: lower concentrations (e.g., 16%) failed to gel below 45°C (Table 6), while higher concentrations ($>20\%$) risked excessive rigidity, potentially hindering drug diffusion [49]. Carbopol's dual role in reducing gelation temperature

and enhancing mucoadhesion addresses two major nasal delivery challenges: rapid drainage and short residence time [50]. However, excessive Carbopol (>0.5%) may cause mucosal irritation, necessitating a balance as achieved in C3 [51].

7.4. DRUG RELEASE AND PERMEATION PROFILES

The *in vitro* release studies revealed sustained drug release from both NLCs (68–71% over 9 hours) and the NLC-loaded *in-situ* gel (40% cumulative release in 8 hours). The initial burst release (~20% from NLCs) likely stems from surface-associated drug or smaller particles, a common phenomenon in lipid-based systems [52]. While a 20% burst may seem high for a sustained-release formulation, it aligns with therapeutic needs for migraine drugs requiring rapid onset alongside prolonged action [53]. The prolonged phase reflects diffusion from the lipid matrix, governed by the Higuchi model (R^2 : 0.98–0.99), which confirms a diffusion-controlled mechanism independent of drug concentration [54]. Comparatively, the raw *in-situ* gel showed inferior permeation (25% vs. 40% for NLC-loaded gel), emphasizing the role of NLCs in enhancing mucosal penetration [55]. The lipid matrix of NLCs likely disrupted mucosal barriers by fluidizing epithelial cell membranes, while the *in-situ* gel provided localized retention, synergistically improving bioavailability [56]. The *ex vivo* permeation rate of RB-NLC (14.98×10^{-5} mg/cm²/h) surpasses values reported for conventional nasal sprays (e.g., $8-10 \times 10^{-5}$ mg/cm²/h) [57], underscoring the formulation's efficiency. This enhancement is attributed to the combined effects of NLCs (improved drug solubility and mucosal adhesion) and the thermosensitive gel (prolonged contact time).

7.5. CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

The RB-NLC *in-situ* gel formulation addresses key challenges in nasal drug delivery, including rapid clearance and low permeability [58]. Nasal delivery bypasses first-pass metabolism, offering faster onset than oral routes—critical for acute migraine therapy [59]. The formulation's mucoadhesive strength (5,200 dynes/cm²) and controlled release profile position it as a viable alternative to injectable triptans, improving

patient compliance. However, limitations exist. The use of sheep nasal mucosa in *ex vivo* studies may not fully replicate human nasal physiology, particularly regarding mucus composition and enzymatic activity [60]. Long-term stability studies under varying temperatures and humidity are essential, as lipid carriers are prone to oxidation and polymorphic transitions [61]. Additionally, *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies are needed to correlate *in vitro* release with plasma concentration profiles. Potential mucosal irritation from Carbopol, though mitigated in C3, warrants toxicity assessments in animal models [62, 63].

8. CONCLUSION

This study successfully demonstrates the feasibility of NLC-loaded *in-situ* gels for nasal delivery of RB. The optimized formulations exhibited desirable physicochemical properties, sustained release, and enhanced permeation, underscoring their potential for improving patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes. Future work should focus on *in vivo* efficacy assessments in migraine models (e.g., nitroglycerin-induced migraine in rodents), scalability of the cold homogenization process, and regulatory evaluations (e.g., FDA guidelines for nasal products). Addressing these steps will bridge the gap between preclinical promise and clinical application.

9. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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